

The Vaults of Sint-Theresia's church in Dilbeek (Belgium): Tradition and Innovation in Tile Vaults in the 20th Century

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Introduction

Tile vaults are a particular type of vault built without centering. Thin bricks (tiles) are placed flatwise, creating a thin surface formed by one or more layers of bricks. The bricks are set with plaster mortar. Plaster mortar hardens very fast, providing a cohesive bond that holds the bricks in place during construction without the need of a centering. The lightness of these vaults, together with the few constructional means that are required, make of this technique a very economic one. Historically, tile vaults have been used in Mediterranean countries, such as Spain, south-east of France, and Italy. At the end of the nineteenth century, Rafael Guastavino (1842-1908) exported this technique to the United States, where he built thousands of vaults. This story is well-known [1]. However, what it is not so well-known is the transmission of tile vaults to the rest of Europe. An ongoing research project about the history of the construction of Belgian vaults has discovered that this technique was introduced in Belgium at the beginning of the twentieth century, not only in churches but also in museums, palaces and other representative buildings [2]. There is no evidence of earlier tile vaults in the country. However, between 1900 and 1950, hundreds of tile vaults were built in Belgium, and several contractors were specialized in this technique.

This paper explains the context of the construction of tile vaults in Belgium and studies the tile vaults of the church of Sint-Theresia van het kind Jezus, in Dilbeek with their innovations in construction and geometry

Tile Vaults Contractors and Patents

Tile vaults appeared in Belgium at the beginning of the twentieth century with no known precedents. The origin of the use of this type of vaults in Belgium was probably France. French contractor Auguste Fabre, who patented several systems for the construction of light vaults, built thousands of tile vaults, in France, Belgium and Algeria [3]. He built the vaults of the Petit-Palais for the 1900 International Exhibition in Paris, designed by the architect Charles Girault. The central dome of this building has a diameter of 24 m [4]. Charles Girault was commissioned to build several buildings for the Belgian king, such as the Royal Palace of Laeken, or the Congo Museum in Tervuren (known nowadays as the Royal Museum for Central Africa). Auguste Fabre built the tile vaults of these buildings with the collaboration of Belgian contractor Charles Daussin. In 1905, Auguste Fabre patented a system of tile vaults in Belgium: *Voûtes économiques* [5]. Two years later, in 1907, Daussin patented *Briques spéciales pour la construction de voûtes légères et système de voûtes* (Special bricks for the construction of light vaults and vault system) [6]. In this patent, Daussin explained a system of vaults built with light bricks, placed flatwise, like in the traditional tile vault construction. The innovation of Daussin was the introduction of special hollow bricks.

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These bricks have concave faces that are filled with plaster mortar or special cement, forming tendons ('Fig. 11' in Fig. 1). The vaults are reinforced with ribs. These ribs are formed by special bricks, with multiple supports for the webs which form the groin ('Fig. 1' and 'Fig. 3' in Fig. 1). If the ribs are visible in the intrados, the piece may have a projection to support the moulding (8 in 'Fig. 1', Fig. 1). Figure 1 shows the different designs of bricks used for different types of vaults: groin vaults ('Fig. 1'), barrel vaults ('Fig. 4'), lunettes or cloister vaults ('Fig. 3'). The bricks may have grooves on the upper face, in order to provide a better connection with an optional layer of mortar that can be reinforced with a wire mesh ('Fig. 11'). Daussin patented the same system in France in 1909 [7].

Figure 1. Drawings in the patent by Charles Daussin, 1907. Joseph Cuvelier Repository. State Archives of Belgium, Brussels.

Daussin's company was very successful. In 1908 he had built more than 200 churches [8]. Charles Daussin died at some point between 1915 and 1919, and the name of the company changed to Vve. Daussin & Tignol. In 1930 the name of the company changed again to J. Tignol & A. Joly. Despite the Company's archives being missing valuable information has been tracked down in its adverts, published in the journals of the time. These adverts contain lists of buildings where the company participated as the contractor of the vaults. More than 70 buildings in Belgium and a dozen in France have been found in these sources.

In a booklet published ca. 1950, Tignol and Joly explained that their vaults were "robust, economic, fast to build, do not need centering, they can be used for large spans, they are light, and have good insulation and acoustic behaviour" [9].

Figure 2. Cover and back page of an advertising booklet by Tignol & Joly, ca. 1955. State Archives of Belgium, Kortrijk, fig

The technique became very popular, and it was explained in some manuals, such as *La construction*, by the major and professor Paul Combaz (1905) or the *Cours d'architecture* by the French architect E. Arnaud (1925) [10].

There were other contractors who specialized in the construction of tile vaults in Belgium. Ernest Sussenaire was a contractor located in Ecaussines, who also patented a system in 1908 [11]. The company Gairin & Brochon advertised the construction of “Voûtes légères et économiques en briques creuses sans armature, ni fer ni bois” (light and economic vaults with hollow bricks, without reinforcement, iron or timber). After their adverts, this company also collaborated in the construction of the vaults of the Royal Palace of Laeken, where Fabre and Daussin participated [12].

The churches by Léonard Homez

Architect Léonard Homez designed three churches in the 1930s: Sainte-Alix in Wolowe-Saint-Pierre (1935-36), Divin Sauveur in Schaerbeek (1935-37), and Sint-Theresia in Dilbeek (1937-39). According to the documentation found for Divin Sauveur and Sainte-Alix, general contractors also offered the construction of the vaults. In the church of Divin Sauveur, the contractor, MM. de Braekeleir and Kallaert included the vaults in the total amount of 461,557.30 francs. A letter from the architect to the Archbishop of Mechelen (4 June 1935) indicated that some modifications were being carried out, including an additional bay, and were leading to an increase of the budget. However, in another letter from the architect to the Archbishop (14 June 1935), the architect explained that the vaults and the ceilings had been directly commissioned to Tignol and Joly, saving 2,000 francs. Later problems with the contractor caused the termination of the contract with Braekeleir and Kallaert, and Joseph De Knoop, who was working at that time as general contractor of Sainte-Alix, finished the general works [13].

A paper about Sainte-Alix and Sint-Theresia was published in the journal *Bâtir* [14], however, there is no much information about the construction of the vaults. Only a short note mentions that “the ribbed vaults in hollow bricks with a natural technique, at the same time rigid, light, lasting, have been built over simple groin templates,

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without formwork or support” and they were built by J. Tignol and A. Joly “d’après leur système bien connu brique et béton” [15].

The naves of Divin Sauveur (Fig. 3, up, left) and Sainte-Alix (Fig. 3, up, right) have a span of 13.25 m and 13.50 m respectively. Both have one single nave covered by an oval barrel vault, with transverse arches dividing the nave, and lunettes. Sainte-Alix has three bays, transept and apse. Groin vaults with lunettes cover the transept and the apse.

Divin Sauveur originally had four bays and the apse, but in the 1960s the architect Jean Dehasse designed a new apse and converted the old one into a transept [16].

The vaults of the two churches are coated in the intrados and on the extrados. However, the bricks can be seen in the intrados through the inner coat. The arches are built in concrete, like the roof trusses [17]. On the extrados, both churches are very similar. A longitudinal concrete beam goes along the crown of the vault, connecting the transverse arches, built in concrete as well. This longitudinal beam is not connected to the vault. At some points of the vaults it is possible to see a wire mesh (Fig. 3, bottom).

Figure 3. Up, left: Church of Divin Sauveur in Schaerbeek; up, right and bottom: Church of Sainte-Alix in Wolowe-Saint-Pierre. Photos: P. Fuentes, 2019.

Sainte-Alix has been surveyed with a laser scanner, and the thickness of the vault is approximately 75 mm in the upper part. It is built with one single layer of bricks, ca. 45 mm thick, plus the layer of mortar over the extrados, ca. 20 mm thick (in the upper part), and the inner coat, ca. 10 mm thick [18]. Due to the form of the vault, in the

lower part of the extrados of the vault the layer of mortar is very thin, and therefore the total thickness is smaller. In this lower part of the first bay it is possible to see the bricks. They measure 300×150 mm, with a thick groove in the middle. The extrados of the lunette is visible in the first bay, and it is built with one part of the bricks used in the vault, broken along the central groove. The fillings of the vault have a height of $1/2$ of the total height of the vault.

The vault of the transept of Sainte-Alix has reinforcement ribs standing out of the extrados (Fig. 3, bottom, right), possibly using the special hollow bricks of Daussin's patent (Fig. 1). These ribs are not visible in the intrados (Fig. 3, up, right).

The vaults of the 1960s-extension of Divin Sauveur are built with a different technique, known as *steengaz*. This system consisted in a metallic wire mesh with ceramic pieces in the crossings. This structure was hung from the upper structure, and, after appropriately shaping the wire, mortar was projected, obtaining a kind of reinforced concrete [19].

The church of Sint-Theresia in Dilbeek

The church is located in Dilbeek, a municipality in the province of Flemish Brabant, in Flanders, very close to Brussels. Nowadays it belongs to the school Regina Caeli.

There is not much documentation about the construction of the church. Architect Léonard Homez was commissioned to design a church in 1936. A tender for the "general work" and "vaults and coating" was called in October 1937: "The submissions of the offers can be done independently for the 'General Works' and for the 'Vaults and Coating'" [20]. The construction of the church was awarded to the contractors Frères Verstraete from Rumbeke, who included in their offer the construction of the vaults for a total amount of 787,750 francs [21]. From this amount, 94,488.55 francs were for the construction of the vaults and coating, that is, 12% of the total amount [22]. The works started by the middle of November 1937 and the dedication of the church took place in May 1939. The previously mentioned article in *Bâtir* in 1939 affirmed that the general contractor was Joseph de Knoop, and that the vaults were built by J. Tignol and A. Joly. However, among the documentation kept at Dilbeek Archive, the Archdiocese of Mechelen and at the school Regina Caeli, nothing has been found about problems with Frères Verstraete [23], and probably this contractor was in charge of the construction during the whole process, commissioning the construction of the vaults to J. Tignol and A. Joly [24]. Only the copies of three of the original drawings have been found and are kept at the school Regina Caeli. They represent the foundations, a plan view and a longitudinal section. In the longitudinal section, the vaults are represented with a total thickness of 100 mm and distinguishing an inner coat around 30 mm thick. This indicates that the architect was aware from the beginning about the system he was going to use to build the vaults (he had already used this system in the churches mentioned above).

The church has six bays covered by a pointed vault and divided by transverse arches. One brick arch and a very narrow bay divide the nave and the apse, covered by a diamond vault (Fig. 4).

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Figure 4. *Sint-Theresia's church in Dilbeek. Intrados and extrados of the vaults. Left: nave; right: apse. Photos: P. Fuentes, 2019.*

The church of Sint-Theresia in Dilbeek has been surveyed with a laser scanner (Fig. 5). The survey was done with 29 scan positions: seven inside the church, at the floor level, four on the extrados of the vaults (three over the vault of the apse, and one beside the vault of the first bay), ten outside the church, and eight additional positions in the sacristy and in the tower in order to join intrados and extrados. The data was registered with the software Faro-Scene.

Access to the extrados of the vaults was only possible in the vault of the first bay, over the gallery (*jubé*) and in the vault of the apse, but not in the vaults of the nave. Therefore, in figure 6 the roof has been drawn following the original drawings by the architect. The thickness is irregular, between 75 and 100 mm. This dimension implies one single layer of bricks, coated in the intrados and on the extrados. Despite this internal coat, the bonding can be seen in the intrados, and the bricks have similar dimensions to the ones in Sainte-Alix. On the extrados it is possible to see a wire mesh, with the horizontal bars placed every 40 cm. The slenderness of the vaults is remarkable, with a ratio of 1/130 (thickness/span).

Figure 5. Sint-Theresia's church in Dilbeek. Orthoimage from the cloud of points. Authors, 2019.

Figure 6. Sint-Theresia's church in Dilbeek. Plan view and longitudinal section. Drawing: Authors, 2019.

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The vault of the nave has an innovative shape. The nave is divided by transverse concrete pointed arches. According to the dimensions stated in the project original drawings, all the bays have a width of 4.40 m (4.00 m between the arches) except the first one, over the gallery (*jubé*), which is 4.80 m wide. The transversal arches span 13.04 m with their centres at a height of 2.63 m above the pavement level, and the intrados highest point 12.00 m high. With these measurements stated in the project, the arches result with an intrados radius of exactly 10.00 m. Between the arches, the vault is formed by two symmetrical shells with double curvature resembling two symmetrical patches of a toroid. At a height of 9.40 m over the floor level, three groins are added forming symmetrical lunettes. The groins DA and DC (Fig. 7) result from the intersection of vertical planes with an ideal barrel vault offset 30 cm from the intrados of the transverse arches. The lunettes frame the pointed barrel vaults perpendicular to the main nave that form the side aisles.

The survey proves that the construction followed the project dimensions with few deviations. The most remarkable is the position of the lunettes' vertex (points D in fig. 7) around 8 cm lower than stated in the project (9.32 m above the pavement level instead of 9.40). The shape of the vault does not correspond with a specific geometric surface. There are slight curvature asymmetries in each shell, consistent with a vault built without formwork with the guide of the main lines: the transversal arches, the central line and the lunettes groins. However, both halves are symmetrical and the vertical rise in the middle of the shells is noticeably constant in the central part (between the lunettes' vertex), even though the shape is slightly flattened at the crown. These features suggest that either the masons were very skilled, or they used some geometric guide to keep a regular form along each half bay (whose span between the arch and the centering of the groin is 2 m). The geometry of the construction main lines is represented in figure 7. The contour lines in figure 10 show the vault shape.

Figure 7. *Sint-Theresia's church in Dilbeek. Left: geometry of the transverse arches and groins of the bays; right: generation of the groins forming the lunettes. Drawing: Authors, 2019.*

The vault of the apse is smaller (8.37×6.55 m). It is covered by a diamond vault. This is the only vault completely accessible on the extrados. The filling in this vault has a height of slightly over 1/3 of the total height of the vault. This is a very low filling compared to traditional tile vaults [25]. The springing of the vault is at 1.73 m above the floor of the apse. Unlike the vault of the nave, the actual geometry does not coincide so well with the designed one. The crown (E in Figs 8-10) is lower than in the original drawings, placed at 8.37 m above the floor. The crown of the vault and the crown of the arch of the north wall (AFG) have the same height, however, the ridge line (EF) is not horizontal but has a curvature, rising 30 cm in the middle point (see longitudinal section in figure 6, above). This dimension coincides with the one given in the original drawings. The wall arches ABC have their crown lower than the crown of the vault, being the difference of heights between points B and E, 2.65 m.

In a plan view, all the groins are practically straight lines. The groins AD are placed forming approximately 30° with the short sides of the vault (Fig. 8). The arches formed by the vault over the walls (ABC and AFG) coincide with arcs of circumference, as well as the presbytery arch. The groins of the vault do not have the form of an arc of circumference. The diagonal groin (AE) fits very well with the ellipse resulting from the intersection of the ideal cylinder formed with by the profile of the arch AFG with the vertical plane formed by the diagonal. Equally, the groin AD fits with the ellipse form by the intersection of the latter cylinder with the vertical plane formed by the groin AD. The design process is like the one used to obtain the lunettes of the nave. It is logical to think that these groins must have been geometrically defined and controlled by a centering or a template, like in the nave.

Figure 8. Sint-Theresia's church in Dilbeek. One quarter of the apse's vault. Levels measured from the springing of the vault, at 1.73 m above the floor. Drawing: Authors, 2019.

The bricks are slightly visible from the interior and it is possible to recognise the bonding. The courses running between the groins have a typical pattern for the construction of the compartments without centering, where the

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bricks form a double curvature surface [26]. The courses form a regular pattern, running practically parallel along each cap. Only a variation is made in the upper part, along the longitudinal crown (EF), where the direction of the bricks changes abruptly, being parallel to the axis of the vault. As far as has been possible, the points of the joints in the intrados have been extracted, and circumferences have been drawn fitting these points. The courses have an inclination and a curvature that vary along the cap, confirming that the caps were built with no templates. The curvature is bigger when the span between the groins is smaller and decreases for larger spans.

It has not been possible to confirm if special pieces, such as the ones in figure 1, were used to reinforce the groins. The bricks are hidden in the intrados and in the extrados, and unlike in Sainte-Alix, no reinforcement ribs stand out of the extrados.

Figure 9. Left and centre: *Sint-Theresia's church in Dilbeek, vault of the apse. Orthoimage and contour lines. Authors, 2019. Right: pattern resulting of a vault built without centering. Lassaulx, 1829.*

Figure 10. *Sint-Theresia's church in Dilbeek. Contour lines of the vaults. Left: third bay of central nave; right: vault of the apse. Drawing: Authors, 2019.*

Conclusions

Between 1900 and 1950, the construction of tile vaults was a common practice in Belgium. The interest on the construction of this type of vaults is revealed not only by the numerous examples that were built, but also by the existence of several contractors specialized in this technique. Vaults were frequently commissioned to these specialized contractors, who also developed and patented their own systems.

Tile vaults were frequently built in churches. Although the principles of the technique are the traditional ones, in this period some innovations were introduced. On the one hand, Historicism was giving way to new forms in architecture; on the other hand, new materials had become popular, and they were also applied to the construction of vaults.

Architect Léonard Homez used tile vaults in three churches built in the 1930s: Saint-Alix in Woluwe-Saint-Pierre, Divin Sauveur in Schaerbeek and Sint-Theresia in Dilbeek. The vaults were built by J. Tignol & A. Joly, successors of Charles Daussin. The geometry of the vaults in these churches shows an evolution. While the two first are very similar, with an oval barrel vault and oval transverse arches, in the latter, the geometry became more complex and pointed forms reminding one of the Gothic style were used. However, the building can hardly be considered a Neo-Gothic church. No ribs are used, and multiple groins with double curvature caps create innovative diamond vaults. The design of the vaults of the nave coincides with minor variations with the dimensions of the original drawings. According to the survey, the construction was carried out using centerings under the groins and building the caps in between “free-hand”, using maybe some devices to control the form, in the same way that traditional tile vaults have been built for centuries. However, these tile vaults are reinforced with a wire mesh, and combined with concrete arches, resulting in a representative example of a period of transition. Historicism was being abandoned, but vaults were still being built, introducing new materials and new forms.

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